

Adversity Quotient of Bachelor of Science in Maritime Information Technology Students at John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc.

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Abstract

This descriptive research was conducted to determine the adversity quotient of the students in Bachelor of Science in Maritime Information Technology (BSMIT) at John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. Respondents of the study were the ninety-five (95) out of one hundred twenty-six (126) or 75.40 percent BSMIT students enrolled during the first semester of school year 2008-2009. A modified standardized instrument, Adversity Quotient questionnaire was used in this study. Results showed that regardless of the grouping, students had “Below Average” adversity quotient. Differences in means and dispersions were observable.

Introduction

College life is another milestone for an individual. Students are confronted with situations different from their high school life. Situations in school combine both favorable and adverse. To whatever extent each situation is being encountered by a student contributes to his or her personality.

Like any other students, students in Bachelor of Science in Maritime Information Technology (BSMIT) at John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. (JBLFMU-Molo) are confronted with varying situations.

AQ is the science of human resilience. According to Stoltz, people who successfully apply this perform optimally in facing adversity—the challenges, big and small that confront us each day. In fact, they not only learn from these challenges, but they also respond to them better and faster (<http://peaklearning.com/>).

This study was made to determine the AQ among BSMIT students on selected variables. Figure 1 depicts the paradigm of the study. It consists of the independent variables, which are the student related factors such as sex and year level and the dependent variable, which is the adversity quotient in the four components namely, Control, Ownership, Reach, and Endurance.

Figure 1: A Schematic Diagram Showing the Relationship among Variables

This study aimed to determine the adversity quotient of BSMIT students at JBLFMU-Molo, Iloilo City during the first semester of school year 2008-2009. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the adversity quotient of students when:
 - a. taken as an entire group?
 - b. grouped according to sex?
 - c. grouped according to year level?
2. What is the students' adversity quotient in each component namely, Control, Ownership, Reach, and Endurance when:
 - a. taken as an entire group?
 - b. grouped according to sex?
 - c. grouped according to year level?

Review of Related Literature

Different persons have different ways of looking at things. Each responds to certain situations differently. Anything that they do constitutes to their personality. A person is a social being, thus, its relationship to every one else is important.

As individuals, they are faced by many good and bad things. Everywhere they go, they are confronted with varying encounters—some are favorable and some are adverse like the student's life. Favorable and adverse situations are inevitable and responding on adverse situations measures one's AQ.

More than 500,000 people worldwide have measured their AQ, by completing the AQ Profile—a series of scientifically engineered questions developed by PEAK Learning. An exceptionally robust measure of resilience, the AQ Profile is the only statistically valid, reliable tool in existence for measuring AQ. The people who have completed this profile reflect a broad range of backgrounds, ages, cultures, industries, and occupations; they have all contributed to the growing AQ global database (<http://www.peaklearning.com/measuring-aq.html>).

Markman(2000) in his study on “Adversity Quotient: The Role of Personal Bounce-Back Ability in New Venture Formation” revealed that AQ, particularly with respect to perceived control over adversities and perceived ownership over the outcomes

of adversities, reliably differentiated between technical inventors who build new organizations and those who merely work for organizations. The study indicated that the higher patent inventors' AQ—which is an acquirable skill—the more financially successful they were. The study assessed the Adversity Quotient (AQ) of 199 patent inventors.

Williams (2003) conducted a study on “The Relationship between Principal Response to Adversity and Student Achievement”. The study involved 17 principals and 79 teachers from the Flagstaff Unified School District of Arizona. The study examined the relationship between principal's response to adversity and student achievement, the relationship between principal and teacher's response to adversity, and principals' perceptions of adversity in education. The results revealed that students attained higher achievement scores in schools with principals with high AQ. It also showed that the teachers' perceived control over their work environment influenced principal/teacher relationships and student achievement.

“Adversity Quotient and the Performance Level of selected Middle Managers of the Different Departments of the City of Manila as revealed by the 360-degree Feedback System” was carried out by Capones (2004). The aim of the research was to determine the relationship between the two variables. The study involved 102 middle managers from 7 departments of the City of Manila. The findings showed that most of respondents had moderate and high AQ. The study also showed evidence for the relationship between adversity quotient and performance ratings as revealed by the 360-degree feedback system.

Villaver (2005) conducted a study on “The Adversity Quotient Levels of Female Grade School Teachers of a Public and a Private School in Rizal Province”. The study focused on examining the significant differences in the Adversity Quotient levels of female grade school teachers of a public and a private school. Respondents involved 105 female grade school teachers, out of which 74 were from a public school and 31 from a private school. The researcher made use of the Adversity Response Profile 7.0 and a demographic questionnaire to obtain relevant background information about the teacher-respondents. The findings concerning AQ and their demographic profile revealed that majority of the respondents that fell under the early adulthood stage category possessed moderate AQ, while their older counterpart possessed moderately low AQ. With respect to civil status, the findings showed that respondents who were single were found to have equal percentages for moderate and moderately low AQ. In addition, it also revealed that simple majority of married respondents possessed moderate AQ level. Teachers who had teaching experience of ten years or lower were found to have moderate AQ, whereas great number of respondents with moderately low AQ were those with eleven to twenty years of experience. Also the findings threw light on the fact that majority of respondents belonging in the lower class socio-economic status had moderate AQ level while those in the middle class had a greater number around the mean of moderately low AQ level. The results of the study also revealed that both public and private female grade school teacher respondents had moderate Adversity Quotient levels. It was also indicated in the study that there was no significant difference exists between the Adversity Quotient level of public and private female grade school teachers.

A study on “Optimism, Adversity and Performance: Comparing Explanatory Style and AQ” was carried out by Johnson (2005). The study aimed to determine the relationship between Explanatory Style and AQ and examine the existence of correlations between each of the constructs and performance in a high-adversity occupation, sales. Respondents in the study were 112 western area sales region of a leading Fortune 500 company in the computer hardware industry. The findings showed that there was a significant relationship between AQ and performance for short term employees.

Haller (2005) conducted a study on “Adversity and Obstacles in the Shaping of Prominent Leaders: A Hermeneutic Phenomenological Inquiry”. Nine primary participants, two current U. S. Senators, a retired U. S. Army Special Forces Major General, a President of a large educational foundation who previously was Chancellor of one major University and President of another, a well-known author and motivational speaker, and the Chairman and Chief Executives Officers of four major companies were involved in the study. The primary participants in the study prior to becoming prominent leaders had experienced various degrees of adversity in their youth and adult lives. Interview was made to collect data. Results revealed that the adversity in the participants’ early lives was not the most important influence and they viewed the obstacles or events in their adult lives as opportunities disguised as challenges. The findings also indicated that overcoming challenges or obstacles strengthened leaders.

A study on “A Study of Adversity Quotient of Secondary School Students In Relation To Their School Performance and the School Climate” was carried by D’souza (2006). Participants were the 548 students from secondary school students studying in the IXth standard of English medium schools of Greater Mumbai. Results showed that there was a significant difference in the adversity quotient for SSC and ICSE and CBSE and SSC school types. It also revealed that the ability to handle adversities at different levels did not differ significantly for the students from different school types.

A study on “Adversity Quotient of Third Year Students in Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management of Colegio del Sagrado Corazon de Jesus” was conducted by Ruedas et. al. (2008). The study was carried out to the 60 students. Results revealed that the students had “below average” adversity quotient ($M=127.10$, $SD=16.992$) when taken as a group. When students were grouped according to gender, both male ($M=128.27$, $SD=19.495$) and female ($M=125.93$, $SD=14.302$) had “below average” adversity quotient. No significant difference in the adversity quotient between male and female was shown.

Research Methodology

This study made use of a descriptive design. The BSMIT students enrolled during the first semester of school year 2008-2009 served as the participants of this study. However, only ninety-five (9) out of one hundred twenty-six (126) or 75.40 percent of the population responded the time when the questionnaire was administered. Then, data were gathered, tallied, computed, interpreted, and analyzed.

Table 1, on next page, shows the distribution of the participants.

Table 1
Distribution of the Participants

Category	f	%
A. Entire Group	95	100.00
B. Sex		
Female	45	47.37
Male	50	52.63
C. Year Level		
First Year	45	47.37
Second Year	12	12.63
Third Year	18	18.95
Fourth Year	20	21.05

In gathering the data for this study, the researchers made use of the Adversity Quotient questionnaire, a modified standardized instrument. To analyze the data, mean and standard deviation were used.

Adversity Response Profile was also used in this study. The AQ Profile is a scale-based, forced-choice questionnaire designed to reveal an individual's response pattern to adverse situations (Stoltz, 1997). It is a normative instrument. Since higher AQ scores reflect greater resilience, they are more desirable than lower scores. In repeated, independent studies conducted by an Educational Testing Service statistician, ETS is the producer of the SAT—the AQ Profile and each of its CORE dimensions has been shown to be highly reliable, or consistent. The AQ Profile has an overall reliability of .88, higher than most popularly accepted psychological instruments and achievement tests (http://peaklearning.com/measuring-aq_arp.html#).

AQ Profile consists of twenty (20) items. Five items correspond to each of the dimensions namely, Control, Ownership, Reach, and Endurance. AQ scores range from 40 to 200, with a global mean of 147.5. In this study the following scorings were observed and descriptions were adopted from the study of Ruedas et. al. (2008).

Each item in the instrument corresponds to a particular dimension of AQ. Items 1, 7, 13, 15, and 17 correspond to Control. Items 2, 6, 11, 16, and 18 correspond to Ownership. Items 3, 5, 9, 12, and 20 correspond to Reach, while the remaining items 4, 8, 10, 14, and 19 correspond to Endurance.

To describe the AQ of students for each dimension, encircled numbers were added and the mean from the answers of all the respondents were computed. Descriptions were based on the following scoring:

Score	Description
21.01 – 25	High

17.01 – 21	Average
13.01 – 17	Below Average
9.01 – 13	Low
5.00 – 9	Very Low

For the description on the students' overall AQ, encircled numbers for all items were added then were multiplied into two (2) and the mean from the answers of all the respondents was computed. Descriptions were based on the following scoring:

Score	Description
168.01 – 200	High
136.01 – 168	Average
104.01 – 136	Below Average
72.01 – 104	Low
40.00 – 72	Very Low

Results

Adversity Quotient of Students

Table 2
Adversity Quotient of BSMIT Students

Category	N	Mean	Description	SD
Entire Group	95	129.07	Below Average	19.792
Sex				
Female	45	129.20	Below Average	22.797
Male	50	128.96	Below Average	16.875
Year Level				
First Year	45	128.76	Below Average	15.143
Second Year	12	123.00	Below Average	16.874
Third Year	18	134.33	Below Average	29.444
Fourth Year	20	128.70	Below Average	20.409

Table 2 shows that the students as an entire group, had “Below Average” AQ (M=129.07, SD=19.792). When students were grouped according to gender, both female (M=129.20, SD=22.797) and male (M=128.96, SD=16.875) also had “Below Average” AQ. When grouped according to year level, all had “Below Average” AQ—first year (M=128.76, SD=15.143), second year (M=123.00, SD=16.874), third year (M=134.33, SD=29.444), and fourth year (M=128.70, SD=20.409).

Dimensions of the AQ of Students

Adversity Quotient (AQ) has four dimensions namely Control, Ownership, Reach, and Endurance.

Table 3

AQ's Control Dimension of BSMIT Students

Category	N	Mean	Description	SD
Entire Group	95	16.47	Below Average	3.083
Sex				
Female	45	16.93	Below Average	3.158
Male	50	16.06	Below Average	2.986
Year Level				
First Year	45	16.38	Below Average	2.774
Second Year	12	16.25	Below Average	3.571
Third Year	18	17.33	Average	3.694
Fourth Year	20	16.05	Below Average	2.946

Table 3 reveals that the AQ's Control dimension of students was "Below Average" (M=16.47, SD=3.083) when taken as an entire group. When grouped according to sex, the AQ's Control dimension for both female (M=16.93, SD=3.158) and male (M=16.06, SD=2.986) was "Below Average". When grouped according to year level, the students' AQ's Control dimension in first year (M=16.38, SD=2.774), second year (M=16.25, SD=3.571), and fourth year (M=16.05, SD=2.946) was also "Below Average". While the third year students (M=17.33, SD=3.694) had an "Average" AQ's Control dimension.

Table 4

AQ's Ownership Dimension of BSMIT Students

Category	N	Mean	Description	SD
Entire Group	95	16.95	Below Average	3.190
Sex				
Female	45	17.49	Average	3.348
Male	50	16.46	Below Average	2.991
Year Level				
First Year	45	17.11	Average	3.221
Second Year	12	16.42	Below Average	2.353
Third Year	18	17.22	Average	3.828
Fourth Year	20	16.65	Below Average	3.100

For the AQ's Ownership dimension, Table 3 reveals that students were "Below Average" (M=16.95, SD=3.19) when taken as an entire group. When grouped according to sex, the AQ's Ownership dimension of female (M=17.49, SD=3.348) students was "Average", while of male (M=16.46, SD=2.991) students was "Below Average". When grouped according to year level, the AQ's Ownership dimension of the first year (M=17.11, SD=3.221) and third year (M=17.22, SD=3.828) students was "Average", while that of the second year (M=16.42, SD=2.353) and fourth year (M=16.65, SD=3.100) students was "Below Average".

Table 5

AQ's Reach Dimension of BSMIT Students

Category	N	Mean	Description	SD
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Entire Group	95	15.62	Below Average	3.262
Sex				
Female	45	15.22	Below Average	3.580
Male	50	15.98	Below Average	2.938
Year Level				
First Year	45	15.20	Below Average	2.889
Second Year	12	14.42	Below Average	2.353
Third Year	18	16.44	Below Average	4.527
Fourth Year	20	16.55	Below Average	2.982

For AQ's Reach dimension, Table 5 shows that students when taken as an entire group (M=15.62, SD=3.262) were said to be "Below Average". When grouped according to sex, the AQ's Reach dimension of both female (M=15.22, SD=3.580) and male (M=15.98, SD=2.938) students was also "Below Average" the same as when grouped according to year level; first year (15.20, SD=2.889), second year (M=14.42, SD=2.353), third year (M=16.44, SD=4.527), and fourth year (M=16.55, SD=2.982).

Table 6
AQ's Endurance Dimension of BSMIT Students

Category	N	Mean	Description	SD
Entire Group	95	15.49	Below Average	3.718
Sex				
Female	45	14.96	Below Average	4.101
Male	50	15.98	Below Average	3.304
Year Level				
First Year	45	15.69	Below Average	2.968
Second Year	12	14.42	Below Average	4.078
Third Year	18	16.17	Below Average	4.756
Fourth Year	20	15.10	Below Average	4.090

For the AQ's Endurance dimension, Table 5 reveals that students when taken as an entire group (M=15.49, SD=3.718) were said to be "Below Average". When grouped according to sex, the AQ's Endurance dimension of both female (M=14.96, SD=4.101) and male (M=15.98, SD=3.304) students was likewise "Below Average" the same result showed when students are grouped according to year level; first year (15.69, SD=2.968), second year (M=14.42, SD=4.078), third year (M=16.17, SD=4.756), and fourth year (M=15.10, SD=4.090).

Conclusions

Based on the results, regardless of the grouping, BSMIT students had "Below Average" AQ. It could be concluded that students are comfort-driven, play it safe, low risk, compatible, settle for good, competent, limited creativity, and cautious about change (<http://www.peaklearning.com/aq-solutions.html>). They are characterized to be under utilization of potential, problems take a significant and unnecessary toll, making climbing difficult, and a sense of helplessness and despair arises from time to time (<http://stitchestm.blogspot.com/2007/09/adversity-quotient-aq-emerging.html>).

With regards to dispersion, AQ of female students was more dispersed than of male students. AQ of third year students was the most dispersed, while of first year was the least dispersed.

In the AQ's Control dimension, the Control of females seemed to be the same as of males, while third year students seemed to be higher than of any other year level. However, the dispersion in the Control of third students was the most dispersed.

With regards to the AQ's Ownership dimension, the Ownership of females seemed to be higher than of males, but dispersion on the Ownership of female students seemed to be higher than of male students. Considering the year level, Ownership of first year students seemed to be the same as with the third year students, while of the second year students seemed to be the same as with the fourth year students. The Ownership of first year and third year students, however, seemed to be higher than that of the second year and fourth year students. The Ownership of third year students was the most dispersed, while least dispersed was of second year students.

The Reach dimension, regardless of groupings, seemed to be the same. Dispersion on Reach dimension of females was higher than of males. With regards to year level, Reach dimension of third year students was the most dispersed, while, least dispersed was of second year students.

The Endurance dimension, regardless of groupings, seemed to be the same as well. The Endurance of females, however, was higher than of males. The Endurance of third year students was the most dispersed, while least dispersed was of first year students.

Differences in some means were observable, but may not significant. Differences among dispersions were also apparent.

Recommendations

The administration and faculty of BSMIT should be cautious in dealing with the students. Their actions might lead to frustrations in some of these students.

There is a need for well-designed activities in school. Curricular and co-curricular activities should be designed in a manner that will improve the AQ of the students.

Further study should be made involving other factors to affirm the results of this study. Studies should also be done integrating activities for the development of the students' AQ.

The same study could be done, but has to cover all the students or sample may be considered but should be drawn randomly.

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